

Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure MIRRI: Partner Charter

(MIRRI-ERIC Partner Charter)

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PURPOSE AND APPLICABILITY

The MIRRI-ERIC Partner Charter defines criteria for the participation of microbial domain biological resource centres (mBRCs), institutions or individuals providing resources, services, training and expertise or participating in joint projects in the frame of the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI). Altogether they are referred to as Partners.

The Partner Charter is binding and shall be agreed between the Partners and the National MIRRI-ERIC Nodes. Partners from countries that are non-signatories to the MIRRI-ERIC or non-existent National MIRRI-ERIC Nodes shall exceptionally agree the Partner Charter with the MIRRI-ERIC legal entity (see section 4 of this charter).

Participation of a Partner in MIRRI is non-exclusive and has no effect on any activity of a Partner outside of MIRRI-ERIC.

Any exceptions regarding the principles specified in this Charter shall follow a transparent decision-making procedure and if applicable a monitored capacity building program according to the Rules of Operation.

The Charter applies together with other MIRRI-ERIC documents and policies listed at the end.

1. GENERAL PRINCIPLES FOR ALL PARTNERS

- (1) Act in compliance with all applicable national, European and international laws.
- (2) Provide annual reports to the National MIRRI-Node in the conformance to the criteria stated in this Charter.
- (3) Ensure to provide a high quality offer of either resources, services, training and expertise. Commit to implement a quality management system and/or quality assurance procedures following appropriate international standards suitable for the respective offer. Partners allow checklists and/or external audits by MIRRI-ERIC to support an adequate evaluation of their knowledge, competence, experience and compliance.
- (4) Agree to be, at any time, transparent to users. Partners will clearly indicate which contributions are part of the MIRRI-ERIC offer, and as such are following MIRRI policies and rules.
- (5) Actively support applicable cluster activities to foster knowledge sharing, innovation and development arising from interaction of users and providers of MIRRI.
- (6) Act within the meaning of Directive 2006/123/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on services in the internal market in order to exclude potential conflicts of interest and guarantee professional diligence and conduct when providing any offer via MIRRI.

- (7) Comply with the MIRRI-ERIC Policy on Intellectual Property Rights.
- (8) Contribute to the MIRRI-ERIC budget according to the fees for Partners defined in the Financial Plan and approved by the Assembly of Members.
- (9) Acknowledge the contribution of MIRRI-ERIC in any publication derived from projects supported by MIRRI-ERIC, according to the principles of good scientific practice.

2. SPECIFIC PRINCIPALS FOR mBRC PARTNERS

- (1) Implement the MIRRI Policies
 - a. to fulfil the MIRRI-ERIC Data Management Policy and provide relevant and predetermined data to the MIRRI-ERIC catalogues following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Data approach.
 - b. for compliance with the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Nagoya Protocol and subsequent regional and national laws.
 - c. on biorisk assessment and biosecurity measures.
 - d. on access for the user community to specialist technologies and skills. Establish a program of authorized physical access to the facilities, scientific equipment and training according to the MIRRI-ERIC Annual Working Plan and decided by the Assembly of Members.
 - e. on a targeted accession of biological material to broaden the range of strains being of high interest for bio-industry and bio-science, financially supported by the respective country. Participate in the mBRCs Directors Forum to contribute to the MIRRI-ERIC Accession Policy and to develop mission/strategy statements that will be included into the annual development of the Accession Policy.
- (2) Actively seek bio-industry interaction to broaden and align the mBRCs portfolio to the market demands.
- (3) Provide annual reports to the National MIRRI-Node on conformance to the MIRRI-ERIC Annual Working Plan and the development of the KPIs (Key Performance Indicators).

3. PRINCIPLES FOR EXTERNAL PARTNERS (FROM NON-MEMBERS AND NON-OBSERVERS)

Partners from countries that are non-signatories to the MIRRI-ERIC Statutes can be exceptionally accepted by the MIRRI-ERIC provided the following conditions are met:

- i. Supply verified added value to the overall MIRRI offer by the candidate partner.

- ii. Support MIRRI-ERIC for negotiations with the respective non-signatory country and encourage the Partner's country to enter into negotiations.

RELATED DOCUMENTS AND POLICIES

The policies cited in this document are available on www.mirri.org/legaldocuments or on request at info@mirri.org:

MIRRI-ERIC Statutes | MIRRI-ERIC Rules of Operation

MIRRI-ERIC Data Management Policy | MIRRI-ERIC Policy on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya Protocol | MIRRI-ERIC Policy on biorisk assessment and biosecurity measures | MIRRI-ERIC Accession Policy | MIRRI-ERIC Policy on Intellectual Property Rights